

**CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEVEL OF SPONTANEOUS
ACTIVATION OF BLOOD BASOPHILS TO TOOTHPASTES IN
CHILDREN WITH ALLERGIC DISEASES**

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Annotation: Many literature data show that plaque is one of the most important etiological and etiopathogenic links in the development of caries and inflammatory periodontal disease, and that effective oral hygiene is the main method of removing plaque. It has been established that the most important and effective way to control plaque is to perform oral hygiene at least 1-2 times a day at home. Traditionally, experts recommend using toothbrushes and toothpaste for this. Toothpaste is a complex system, the formation of which includes abrasives, humectants, binders, foaming agents, surfactant components, perfume fillers, and pharmaceutical additives. Toothpaste is designed for specific user groups, taking into account age and the state of oral organs and tissues. The effectiveness of toothpaste has been proven by recent studies [1-7]. But today when choosing toothpaste, somatic diseases in children are not taken into account. Up to 30% of the population in highly developed countries suffers from allergic diseases. Prevalence of atopic (IgE antibody-mediated) diseases: the incidence of atopic dermatitis in the population is 10-15%, allergic rhinitis - 23-28%, bronchial asthma - 5.4%. In 40-60% of patients, complex allergic damage to the skin, respiratory tract, and gastrointestinal tract is detected [8]. The increase in the incidence of allergic diseases indicates that environmental factors have an impact on the manifestation of genetic predisposition. Functional gene polymorphisms may determine differences in vulnerability to environmental factors, highlighting the complexity of gene-environment interactions. This area is not yet well understood. Currently,

CAST tests are used to diagnose allergies. This method has 100% specificity, which greatly complements the measurement of IgE antibodies. The use of CAST tests avoids the use of life-threatening induced tests and does not pose any risk to the patient [9-11]. The CAST test has been found to be applicable to the diagnosis of drug allergies to antibiotics, painkillers, anesthetics, muscle relaxants, etc., as well as allergies to insect bites (bees, wasps, cockroaches, fleas), inhalation allergens, and food additives (preservatives, coloring agents). Specialized allergens (latex, chloramine, formaldehyde, etc.).

The aim of the study is: to investigate the spontaneous activation of peripheral basophils against toothpaste in children with a history of severe allergies.

Materials and Methods: We were contacted about dental treatment from 3 children aged 10 to 94 years. The children were divided into 2 groups. The first group included children with allergies (47 children) who had a history of allergic reactions and were recorded by an allergist. The 2nd group included children (47 people) with no history of allergic reactions. In all children, the intensity of the progression of caries is determined by the index CP (dental caries lesions of temporary teeth + filled false teeth) for milk teeth, and the index CP + CP (dental caries lesions of temporary teeth + filled false teeth + dental caries lesions of permanent teeth + filled permanent teeth + removed permanent teeth) for mixed bite. To clarify the possibility of using toothpaste, all children were sent to measure the antigen-induced response of basophilic activation using the flow-CAST method. Prior to the study, informed consent was obtained from parents. The technique is based on the ability of basophils to express activation and degranulation markers on their surface after incubating with the allergen under study when the patient is sensitized to the allergen. Markers such as the LAMP family molecules (CD63, CD107a) and the CD203c molecule, a specific marker of basophils, can be easily identified on the cell surface using a flow cytometer. CD203c is the most specific and beneficial marker of basophilic activation. This

molecule is a multifunctional external enzyme involved in the decomposition of many molecules. The CD203c molecule is not detected in other leukocyte populations, and this molecule is expressed only in basophils and mast cells. When cells are activated by allergens, the expression level of CD203c increases significantly. Patients are tested for spontaneous activation of basophils - the percentage of activated basophilic granulocytes CD3-CRTH2+ CD203c++ in the sample with buffer, induced activation of basophils - the percentage of CD3-CRTH2+CD203c++ cells in the sample with positive controls (anti-positive controls - IgE antibodies), and as well as test allergens. To determine the degree of activation of basophils, the activation index, that is, the ratio of induced activation of basophils by allergens and spontaneous activation by buffer has been proposed. If the activation index exceeds 1.05, the presence of induced activation of basophils against the allergen used is noted. All children were tested using the following toothpaste. PRO "Bracket Ortho"; * R.O.C.S. BABY "fragrant chamomile"; * R.O.C.S. Kids "Barberry". • R.O.C.S. "Active calcium"; * R.O.C.S. PRO "Young & White Enamel". As a result of the study, it was found that the intensity of the caries process in children with allergies is 3.45 ± 0.12 , whereas in children in the control group it is 6.73 ± 0.12 . This is due to the low intake of flour and sweet products in children with allergies. Children with allergies brushed their teeth 1-1 times a day on average, and children in the control group also brushed their teeth 1-1 times a day on average. According to the survey, for every child toothpaste and toothbrush were selected by dentists. On average, 1 package of toothpaste was sufficient for 2 months, while 9 cases in the control group showed excessive use of toothpaste (1 package ran out in 1 month). In children in both study groups, toothbrushes were replaced after 1-4 months. In the first group of studies, the average value of peripheral blood immunoglobulin E was 93.76 ± 4.65 IU/ml and basic basophil activity was $6.58 \pm 0.12\%$. As a result of the study, peripheral blood was added to R.O.C.S. We found that incubating with toothpaste reduced the

average number of activated basophils in a group of children with a history of severe allergies. PRO "Bracket Ortho" ranged from $6.58 \pm 0.12\%$ to $7.66 \pm 0.08\%$, with a basophil activity ratio of 1.08. R.O.C.Activation coefficient of peripheral blood basophils in children of the first group when incubated with S-toothpaste. BABY "Scented Chamomile", R.O.C.S. When incubated with toothpaste, it was 1.04.Kids "Barberry" - 1.11, R.O.C.S When cultured with toothpaste. "Active calcium" - R.O.C.S When cultured with toothpaste, 1.04. PRO "Young & White Enamel" - 1.05.In the 2nd group of children without allergies, the concentration of total immunoglobulin E in peripheral blood averaged 74.46 ± 4.19 IU/ml and basic basophil activity was 6.93 ± 0.15 .The results of the study, R.O.C.S.It was found that during the culture of peripheral blood with toothpaste, the average number of activated basophils in a group of children with a history of allergies without load decreases. PRO "Bracket Ortho" ranged from $6.93 \pm 0.15\%$ to $7.97 \pm 0.07\%$, with a basophil activity ratio of 1.04. R.O.C.S. Activation coefficient of peripheral blood basophils in children of the 2nd group in incubation with toothpaste. BABY "Scented Chamomile", R.O.C.S. When incubated with toothpaste, it was 1.04.Kids "Barberry" - 1.09, R.O.C.S When cultured with toothpaste. "Active calcium" - R.O.C.S When cultured with toothpaste, 1.04. PRO "Young & White Enamel" - 1.05.The data obtained are consistent with the studies of other authors that, despite the complex composition of toothpaste, which guarantees its effectiveness against plaque, it can cause sensitization of the body both in children with already a history of allergies and in children with previously undetected clinical symptoms.Symptoms allergy.The use of methods to assess the spontaneous activation of basophils is a very specific and safe research method for determining the risk of contact dermatitis in patients with a serious history of allergies.Oral hygiene products should be selected individually for patients of this category.The components of toothpaste can act as contact allergens, and if swallowed, can act as food allergens.For children from 3 to 10 years of age with allergic diseases,

R.O.C.It was detected that the activation level of peripheral blood basophils for S toothpaste was low (within the reference value). BABY "Scented Chamomile", R.O.C.S. "Active Calcium", R.O.C.S. PRO "Young & White Enamel".

Conclusion: These pastes can be recommended for children with allergic diseases.

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